

New Orthogonal Extension Methods for Tree-Structured Filter Banks

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ABSTRACT

When processing finite length sequences via paraunitary filter banks, a commonly used technique consists of artificially extending the signal before the analysis stage. The use of the extension methods avoids the border effects, and perfect reconstruction, even orthogonal, size-limited filter banks can be defined. In this paper we first characterize and generate all signal extension methods which yield orthogonal subband transforms. Secondly, the particular case of non-circular orthogonal extension methods is investigated, and the first general design method of non-circular orthogonal extensions is derived. Finally, the computational cost of the design algorithm is evaluated and compared to that of orthogonal boundary filter generation methods.

1 INTRODUCTION

Signal extension methods have been extensively used for subband processing of finite length signals [1, 2, 6, 7]. The most popular examples of this kind of techniques are the periodic extension, that leads to an orthogonal subband transform, and the symmetric extension, which does not preserve the orthogonality of the filter bank, but only the perfect reconstruction property. Although some other techniques have been proposed, none of them leads to orthogonal transforms, and additional requirements such as frequency selectivity or smoothness of the extension have not been theoretically treated either.

In this paper we analyze first the existence of new orthogonal extension methods that lead to orthogonal subband transforms for finite length signals. Considering a paraunitary FIR two-channel filter bank and any linear extension method we construct their associated transformation matrix as described in [3, 4]. This characterization of the transformation operator lets us state the problem of designing extension methods with the extra property of orthogonality. Thus, we obtain the conditions to be satisfied by the transformation matrix to be orthogonal; moreover, we provide a general method for the design of orthogonal extensions.

In the second part of the paper we focus on a particular type of orthogonal extensions: the non-circular ones.

An extension is said to be non-circular if the artificial samples at one border only depend on the original samples at the same border. We present a characterization and a general design method of non-circular orthogonal extension matrices.

Note that every transformation matrix associated to any extension method also provides a set of border filters as defined in [5]. In this way, the algorithm for the design of orthogonal extensions presented here can also be considered as a method for designing orthogonal boundary filters. In section 5 we compare the computational cost of our algorithm to that of classical boundary filter design [5].

2 NOTATION

Throughout this paper, vectors are denoted by lower case letters ($\mathbf{h}$), and matrices by upper case letters, fixing their size ($\mathbf{H} = \mathbf{H}_{m \times n}$). The null matrix and the identity matrix (of order N) are represented by $\mathbf{0}_N$ and $\mathbf{I}_N$ respectively.

We consider the paraunitary filter bank given by the low pass filter $\mathbf{h} = [h(0), h(1), \dots, h(L-1)]$ and the associated high pass filter $\mathbf{g} = [h(L-1), -h(L-2), \dots, h(1), -h(0)]$. We will assume that the length of these filters is $L = 2K + 2$, with K even. We build the matrix $\mathbf{H}_{m \times (m+2K)}$ whose m rows contain the prototype filters, adding zeros when necessary. In sake of simplicity, we will write $\mathbf{H}_{m \times (m+2K)}$ as a block Toeplitz form [3, 5]:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{A}_K & \dots & \mathbf{A}_0 & \mathbf{0}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{0}_2 \\ \mathbf{0}_2 & \mathbf{A}_K & \dots & \mathbf{A}_0 & \ddots & \vdots \\ \vdots & \ddots & \ddots & \dots & \ddots & \mathbf{0}_2 \\ \mathbf{0}_2 & \dots & \mathbf{0}_2 & \mathbf{A}_K & \dots & \mathbf{A}_0 \end{bmatrix}$$

where, for all $j = 0, \dots, K$,

$$\mathbf{A}_j = \begin{bmatrix} h(2j+1) & h(2j) \\ -h(L-2j-2) & h(L-2j-1) \end{bmatrix}$$

In particular, $\mathbf{H}_{K \times 3K}$ can be split into three block-Toeplitz submatrices of order K : $\mathbf{H}_{K \times 3K} = [\mathbf{D} \ \mathbf{E}$

F]. $\mathbf{D}$ and $\mathbf{F}$ are, respectively, upper and lower block-triangular matrices.

Let us consider a finite signal $\mathbf{x}$ of even length $N \geq 2K$, with $\mathbf{x} = [\mathbf{x}(0), \mathbf{x}(1), \dots, \mathbf{x}(N-1)]^T = [\mathbf{x}_a^T \ \mathbf{x}_c^T \ \mathbf{x}_b^T]^T$, where $\mathbf{x}_a$ and $\mathbf{x}_b$ contain, respectively, the first and last K components of $\mathbf{x}$, and $\mathbf{x}_c$ the remaining central ones. We define an extension of $\mathbf{x}$ as the vector $\mathbf{x}_e = [\mathbf{x}_l^T, \mathbf{x}^T, \mathbf{x}_r^T]^T$. This extension is linear if $\mathbf{x}_l$ and $\mathbf{x}_r$ depend linearly on $\mathbf{x}$, that is, if there exist left and right extension matrices ($\mathbf{C}^{l,a}, \mathbf{C}^{l,c}, \mathbf{C}^{l,b}$ and $\mathbf{C}^{r,a}, \mathbf{C}^{r,c}, \mathbf{C}^{r,b}$) such that $\mathbf{x}_l = \mathbf{C}^{l,a}\mathbf{x}_a + \mathbf{C}^{l,c}\mathbf{x}_c + \mathbf{C}^{l,b}\mathbf{x}_b$ and $\mathbf{x}_r = \mathbf{C}^{r,a}\mathbf{x}_a + \mathbf{C}^{r,c}\mathbf{x}_c + \mathbf{C}^{r,b}\mathbf{x}_b$.

In this work we consider the following transformations: $\mathbf{y}_e = \mathbf{H}_{N \times (N+2K)}\mathbf{x}_e$. This is equivalent to process the signal $\mathbf{x}_e$ by means of the analysis filter bank given by $\mathbf{h}$ and $\mathbf{g}$, only retaining the N central output samples. The whole transformation of the original signal $\mathbf{x}$ can be expressed as $\mathbf{y}_e = \mathbf{G}\mathbf{x}$ where the transformation matrix is, whenever $N \geq 3K$, [3, 4]

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,a} + \mathbf{E} \ \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,c} + [\mathbf{F} \ \mathbf{0}_{K \times (N-3K)}] & \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,b} \\ & \mathbf{H}_{(N-2K) \times N} \\ \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a} & \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,c} + [\mathbf{0}_{K \times (N-3K)} \ \mathbf{D}] \ \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b} \end{bmatrix}.$$

3 GENERATION OF ORTHOGONAL EXTENSION METHODS

Our aim is to develop a general method for designing orthogonal matrices $\mathbf{G}$. First of all, we can show that a necessary condition for $\mathbf{G}$ to be orthogonal is that $\mathbf{C}^{l,c}, \mathbf{C}^{r,c}$ are null [4]. For this reason, it is sufficient to study the orthogonality of matrices $\mathbf{G}$ of the type:

$$\mathbf{G} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,a} + \mathbf{E} & \mathbf{F} \ \mathbf{0}_{K \times (N-3K)} & \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,b} \\ & \mathbf{H}_{(N-2K) \times N} & \\ \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a} & \mathbf{0}_{K \times (N-3K)} & \mathbf{D} \ \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b} \end{bmatrix}.$$

Secondly, we have proven that $\mathbf{D}, \mathbf{E}, \mathbf{F}$ can be written in the following way [4]:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{F} = \mathbf{R}_0\mathbf{P}_0 = \mathbf{Q}_0\mathbf{K}_F\mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{D} = \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{P}_1 = \mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{K}_D\mathbf{P}_1 \\ \mathbf{E} = \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}_0 - \mathbf{R}_0\mathbf{C}^T\mathbf{P}_1 \end{cases} \quad (1)$$

where both $[\mathbf{Q}_0\mathbf{Q}_1]$ and $[\mathbf{P}_0^T\mathbf{P}_1^T]$ are orthogonal matrices, and $\mathbf{K}_F, \mathbf{K}_D$ are non-singular square matrices of order $K/2$ such that [4]

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{K}_F(\mathbf{C}^T\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{I}_{K/2})\mathbf{K}_F^T = \mathbf{I}_{K/2} \\ \mathbf{K}_D(\mathbf{C}\mathbf{C}^T + \mathbf{I}_{K/2})\mathbf{K}_D^T = \mathbf{I}_{K/2} \end{cases} \quad (2)$$

The result we have obtained is summarized in the following theorem, whose proof is shown in Appendix 1:

Theorem 1 $\mathbf{G}$ is orthogonal if and only if there exists any orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_1 & \mathbf{V}_2 \\ \mathbf{V}_3 & \mathbf{V}_4 \end{bmatrix}$ of order K

such that

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,a} = \mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{V}_1\mathbf{P}_0 - \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,b} = \mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{V}_2\mathbf{P}_1 \\ \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a} = \mathbf{Q}_0\mathbf{V}_3\mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b} = \mathbf{Q}_0\mathbf{V}_4\mathbf{P}_1 + \mathbf{R}_0\mathbf{C}^T\mathbf{P}_1 \end{cases} \quad (3)$$

In this way, we have obtained not only a characterization for orthogonal matrices $\mathbf{G}$, but also the most general method for designing any orthogonal transform $\mathbf{G}$. It suffices to choose an orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{V}$ and introduce it into the expressions (3). As any orthogonal matrix of order K is defined by $K(K-1)/2$ parameters, there are $K(K-1)/2$ degrees of freedom for constructing $\mathbf{G}$.

4 GENERATION OF ORTHOGONAL NON-CIRCULAR TRANSFORMS

We say that a signal extension is non-circular if $\mathbf{C}^{r,a}$ and $\mathbf{C}^{l,b}$ are null. The periodic extension is circular, and it is well known that its associated transform matrix is orthogonal. We are interested in the design of orthogonal non-circular transforms $\mathbf{G}$. With this aim, we derive the following result from Theorem 1:

Corollary 1 If $\mathbf{G}$ is an orthogonal matrix and any of the matrices $\mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,b}, \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a}$ is null, then the other one must be null. Moreover, a non-circular matrix $\mathbf{G}$ is orthogonal if and only if there exist orthogonal matrices $\mathbf{V}_1, \mathbf{V}_4$ of order $K/2$ such that

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,a} = \mathbf{Q}_1\mathbf{V}_1\mathbf{P}_0 - \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{C}\mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b} = \mathbf{Q}_0\mathbf{V}_4\mathbf{P}_1 + \mathbf{R}_0\mathbf{C}^T\mathbf{P}_1 \end{cases}$$

In this case there are $K(K-2)/4$ degrees of freedom for designing $\mathbf{G}$. The proof is straightforward from Theorem 1: $\mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,b} = \mathbf{0}_K$ if and only if $\mathbf{V}_2 = \mathbf{0}_{K/2}$. As $\mathbf{V}$ is orthogonal, this happens if and only if $\mathbf{V}_3$ is null and both $\mathbf{V}_1$ and $\mathbf{V}_4$ are orthogonal, which finishes the proof.

Remark 1 Note that the rows of $\mathbf{G}$ directly provide edge filters. We will compare the proposed method to the traditional border filter design algorithm given in [5]. This algorithm provides all sets of non-circular orthogonal border filters, while the method presented in Corollary 1 designs all sets of solutions associated to signal extensions. However, from any orthogonal non-circular extension matrix, we can left multiply $[\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{l,a} \ \mathbf{F}]$ by any K -order orthogonal matrix so as to obtain any set of non-circular left edge filters, and left multiply $[\mathbf{D}\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b}]$ by another one, for deriving all right edge filters. In this case, both methods lead to the same solutions. In the next section we will also compare their computational complexities.

5 COMPUTATIONAL COST

The first step in the orthogonal extensions generation process is the construction of the basic matrices

$\mathbf{P}_0$, $\mathbf{Q}_0$, $\mathbf{K}_F$ and $\mathbf{C}$. It can be shown that $\mathbf{P}_1$, $\mathbf{Q}_1$, $\mathbf{K}_D$ can be derived from these basic matrices after some alternating sign changes. Thus, the basic matrices only depend on the prototype filters, and can be computed once for all. Hence, when evaluating the cost of our algorithm we should take into account two different steps: 1) construction of the basic matrices, and 2) substitution of the input orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{V}$ into the generation formula given in (3).

1. **Construction of the basic matrices:** In order to obtain the decomposition $\mathbf{F} = \mathbf{Q}_0 \mathbf{K}_F \mathbf{P}_0$ we must apply the QR factorization in two steps, one for orthogonalizing its rows and one for its columns. This is achieved in this way:

- First, we build $\mathbf{F}_{odd}$ from the $K/2$ odd rows of $\mathbf{F}$; they are linearly independent because $h(0)$ is nonzero. Due to the block-Toeplitz structure of $\mathbf{F}$, its remaining rows can be written as $\mathbf{T}_{even} \mathbf{F}_{odd}$, being $\mathbf{T}_{even}$ a lower Toeplitz triangular matrix of size $K/2$. In order to get $\mathbf{T}_{even}$, $\frac{K^3}{8} + \frac{K^2}{4}$ operations are required.
- Secondly, we apply the Gram-Schmidt orthogonalization procedure to the rows of $\mathbf{F}_{odd}$. Because of its lower block-triangular structure, only $\frac{K^3}{12} + \frac{K^2}{4} + \frac{2K}{3}$ products are needed to decompose $\mathbf{F}_{odd} = \mathbf{T}_{odd} \mathbf{P}_0$, where $\mathbf{T}_{odd}$ is lower triangular of size $K/2$ and $\mathbf{P}_0$ has orthonormal rows.
- Next, $\mathbf{R}_0 = \mathbf{F} \mathbf{P}_0^T$ is a lower triangular matrix whose odd rows form $\mathbf{T}_{odd}$, while its even rows form the lower triangular product matrix $\mathbf{T}_{even} \mathbf{T}_{odd}$. Its computation involves $\frac{K^3}{48} + \frac{K^2}{8} + \frac{K}{6}$ operations.
- Again, the orthogonalization of the $K/2$ independent columns of $\mathbf{R}_0$ is fast due to its lower triangular structure. This way, after other $\frac{K^3}{12} + \frac{K^2}{4} + \frac{2K}{3}$ operations, we derive $\mathbf{Q}_0$ with orthonormal columns and $\mathbf{K}_F$ lower triangular such that $\mathbf{R}_0 = \mathbf{Q}_0 \mathbf{K}_F$.

Finally, if we build $\mathbf{P}_1$, $\mathbf{Q}_1$, $\mathbf{K}_D$ from these basic matrices, then $\mathbf{K}_D \mathbf{C} = \mathbf{K}_F \mathbf{C}^T = \mathbf{Q}_1^T \mathbf{E} \mathbf{P}_0^T$. By exploiting the particular structure of the matrices appearing in this triple product, it can be accomplished after $\frac{3K^3}{8} + \frac{3K^2}{4}$ operations. Therefore, the whole computational cost of the basic matrices associated to the prototype filters amounts to $\frac{9K^3}{16} + \frac{3K^2}{2} + \frac{13K}{6}$ operations.

2. **Construction of the extension from the basic matrices:** Given any input orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{V}$ of order $\mathbf{K}$, we have to compute

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{D} \mathbf{C}^{l,a} &= \mathbf{Q}_1 (\mathbf{V}_1 - \mathbf{K}_D \mathbf{C}) \mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{D} \mathbf{C}^{l,b} &= \mathbf{Q}_1 \mathbf{V}_2 \mathbf{P}_1 \\ \mathbf{F} \mathbf{C}^{r,a} &= \mathbf{Q}_0 \mathbf{V}_3 \mathbf{P}_0 \\ \mathbf{F} \mathbf{C}^{r,b} &= \mathbf{Q}_0 (\mathbf{V}_4 + \mathbf{K}_F \mathbf{C}^T) \mathbf{P}_1 \end{aligned}$$

Each one of these expressions involve a triple matrix product where the first and the last matrices are block-triangular; because of it, only $\frac{3K^3}{8} + \frac{3K^2}{4}$ operations are required.

The computational complexities (measured as the number of multiplications) of the different steps of the proposed algorithm are summarized in Table 1; in the last column the computation cost of the basic matrices has been added to the extension design cost.

TABLE 1: Complexity of the design method

	Extension design	Total cost
Circular	$\frac{3K^3}{2} + 3K^2$	$\frac{33K^3}{16} + \frac{9K^2}{2} + \frac{13K}{6}$
Non-Circular	$\frac{3K^3}{4} + \frac{3K^2}{2}$	$\frac{21K^3}{16} + 3K^2 + \frac{13K}{6}$

As explained in Remark 1, now we compare our method to the traditional boundary filter design algorithm given in [5]. In Appendix 2 it is shown that the complexity of this algorithm amounts to $16K^3 + 56K^2 + 40K$. Table 1 assures that the computational cost of the proposed method is lower in any case. Moreover, recall that we must compare the complexity of the border filter design (i.e. $O(16K^3)$) to our non-circular result (i.e. $O(21K^3/16)$), because the boundary filter design method only provides non-circular solutions. As a conclusion, we can state that our method is about 12 times faster than the border filter design algorithm. In case we also make the additional products addressed in Remark 1, the complexity of the our method would be increased in $\frac{5K^3}{4} + K^2$ operations for each border, so the global cost would be $O(61K^3/16)$, at least four times faster than the traditional algorithm.

6 CONCLUSIONS

In this paper we have presented a general design method for signal extensions which yield orthogonal subband transforms. Moreover, all non-circular orthogonal extensions have been characterized and constructed from a new design algorithm. It has also been shown that this algorithm provides any set of orthogonal boundary filters, with lower complexity than other traditional algorithms. Current research is being oriented to the optimization of properties of the non-circular orthogonal extensions, such as smoothness, and frequency selectivity of the associated boundary filters.

APPENDIX 1: PROOF OF THEOREM 1.

It is sufficient to study the orthogonality of matrices $\mathbf{G}$ of order $4K$ of this kind:

$$\begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{D} \mathbf{C}^{l,a} & \mathbf{F} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{D} \mathbf{C}^{l,b} \\ \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{E} & \mathbf{F} & \mathbf{0} \\ \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{E} & \mathbf{F} \\ \mathbf{F} \mathbf{C}^{r,a} & \mathbf{0} & \mathbf{D} & \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{F} \mathbf{C}^{r,b} \end{bmatrix}. \quad (4)$$

Let us impose the block-rows of this matrix to be orthonormal. For this purpose, we regard the orthonormality of the block-rows of $\mathbf{H}$, that is,

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{D}\mathbf{D}^T + \mathbf{E}\mathbf{E}^T + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{F}^T = \mathbf{I}_K \\ \mathbf{E}\mathbf{D}^T + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{E}^T = \mathbf{0}_K \\ \mathbf{F}\mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{D}\mathbf{F}^T = \mathbf{0}_K \end{cases} \quad (5)$$

Now, by using (1) and (5), it is easy to see that orthogonality of any two different block-rows of (4) is equivalent to

$$\begin{aligned} 1) & \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,a}\mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{0}_K \implies \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,a} = \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{C}_1\mathbf{P}_0 \\ 2) & \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,b}\mathbf{F}^T = \mathbf{0}_K \implies \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,b} = \mathbf{R}_1\mathbf{C}_2\mathbf{P}_1 \\ 3) & \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a}\mathbf{D}^T = \mathbf{0}_K \implies \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a} = \mathbf{R}_0\mathbf{C}_3\mathbf{P}_0 \\ 4) & \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b}\mathbf{F}^T = \mathbf{0}_K \implies \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b} = \mathbf{R}_0\mathbf{C}_4\mathbf{P}_1 \\ 5) & (\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,a})(\mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a})^T + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,b}(\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b})^T = \mathbf{0}_K \end{aligned}$$

We substitute the matrices obtained in 1), 2), 3), 4) into 5), and finally we impose the orthonormality of the block-rows $[\mathbf{E} + \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,a} \ \mathbf{F} \ \mathbf{D}\mathbf{C}^{i,b}]$ and $[\mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,a} \ \mathbf{D} \ \mathbf{E} + \mathbf{F}\mathbf{C}^{r,b}]$ separately. By using the properties (5) and (2), we simplify and obtain:

$$\begin{cases} \mathbf{C}_1\mathbf{C}_1^T + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{C}_1^T + \mathbf{C}_1^T\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{C}_2\mathbf{C}_2^T = \mathbf{I}_{K/2} \\ \mathbf{C}_3\mathbf{C}_3^T - \mathbf{C}^T\mathbf{C}_4^T - \mathbf{C}_4\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{C}_4\mathbf{C}_4^T = \mathbf{I}_{K/2} \\ (\mathbf{C} + \mathbf{C}_1)\mathbf{C}_3^T + \mathbf{C}_2(\mathbf{C}_4^T - \mathbf{C}) = \mathbf{0}_{K/2} \end{cases}$$

Let us define

$$\mathbf{A} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{C} + \mathbf{C}_1 & \mathbf{C}_2 \\ \mathbf{C}_3 & \mathbf{C}_4 - \mathbf{C}^T \end{bmatrix};$$

the last three expressions and (2) assure that $\mathbf{A}\mathbf{A}^T = \text{diag}(\mathbf{I} + \mathbf{C}\mathbf{C}^T, \mathbf{I} + \mathbf{C}^T\mathbf{C}) = \text{diag}(\mathbf{K}_D^{-1}\mathbf{K}_D^{-T}, \mathbf{K}_F^{-1}\mathbf{K}_F^{-T})$, so there must be an orthogonal matrix $\mathbf{V} = \begin{bmatrix} \mathbf{V}_1 & \mathbf{V}_2 \\ \mathbf{V}_3 & \mathbf{V}_4 \end{bmatrix}$ such that $\mathbf{A} = \text{diag}(\mathbf{K}_D^{-1}, \mathbf{K}_F^{-1})\mathbf{V}$. Identifying block by block,

$$\begin{aligned} \mathbf{C}_1 &= \mathbf{K}_D^{-1}\mathbf{V}_1 - \mathbf{C} & \mathbf{C}_2 &= \mathbf{K}_D^{-1}\mathbf{V}_2 \\ \mathbf{C}_3 &= \mathbf{K}_F^{-1}\mathbf{V}_3 & \mathbf{C}_4 &= \mathbf{K}_F^{-1}\mathbf{V}_4 + \mathbf{C}^T \end{aligned}$$

It suffices to substitute them into 1), 2), 3), 4) in order to obtain the desired extension matrices.

APPENDIX 2: COMPLEXITY OF THE BOUNDARY FILTER DESIGN ALGORITHM.

The idea of this algorithm is that the left edge filters are found as K new rows that are attached to matrix $\mathbf{H}$ in at least K iterations. Initially, we set $\mathbf{S}_0 = \mathbf{H}_{(L+2) \times 2L}$ and $i = 0$. While $i < K$, a random row vector is projected over the orthogonal complement of the subspace spanned by the rows of $\mathbf{S}_i$. If the projected vector is nonzero, it is attached to $\mathbf{S}_i$ as a new first row so as to form matrix $\mathbf{S}_{i+1}$, and we set $i = i + 1$.

For evaluating the complexity of this algorithm, we will suppose that, for each row, a single iteration is needed, that is, at every step the projected random vector is nonzero. Thus, we will consider the optimum performance

conditions for this algorithm. The special structure of $\mathbf{H}$ will be also exploited.

The study of the computational cost of the algorithm is as follows: for $i = 0, \dots, K-1$, at the $(i+1)$ -th iteration $\mathbf{S}_i$ has size $(L+2+i) \times 2L$; a random vector of length L has to be built ($3L$ operations) and extended with L zeroes so as to form $\mathbf{v}$. The product $\mathbf{v}^T\mathbf{S}_i^T\mathbf{S}_i$ and its normalization involve $\frac{3L^2}{2} + (2i+5L)$ multiplications. It suffices to compute the whole sum $\frac{3L^2}{2} + (2i+8L)$, varying $i = 0, \dots, K-1$. Finally we substitute $L = 2K+2$ and obtain $8K^3 + 28K^2 + 20K$; this quantity must be doubled because the same complexity is necessary for the right edge filters. We conclude that this algorithm requires at least $16K^3 + 56K^2 + 40K$ operations.

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